

A federated paradigm of real-world data sources utilization for the empowerment of diagnosis, prognosis, and risk assessment of cardiovascular conditions

D1.5 CVDLINK public website

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Project Information

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Project Summary

In the EU, more than 6 million new cardiovascular disease (CVD) cases and 1.8 million deaths are reported yearly, imposing a substantial burden on national healthcare systems and society in general. The development of effective preventive interventions, adopted for each individual and population, will reduce the overall cost of patient management and justify the assertion that CVDs can be prevented and controlled. The exploration of existing clinical, genetic, and real-world data sources can contribute to these goals. However, several challenges related to data availability, management, and processing complicate this process. The 48-month CVDLINK project aims to tackle these challenges by implementing a privacy-by-design European-wide federated platform-as-a-service (PaaS) to deliver effective data-driven human-centric interventions and advance research and management in the CVD domain. CVDLINK is based on two major offerings: (1) the seamless and legally compliant integration, secure sharing, and automated curation of existing data, and (2) a set of AI and data-enabled precision medicine tools and pipelines for better diagnosis, risk stratification, and treatment of CVDs. The project will examine seven different cardiovascular conditions, making use of retrospective datasets, cohort studies, and biobanks from seven countries, aiming to demonstrate how heterogeneous data sources can be effectively exploited to build comprehensive AI-driven tools to benefit health systems, patients, industry, and EU citizens. The developed tools will be validated in five countries, demonstrating the impact of the CVDLINK outputs. Additionally, the project will generate a set of best practices which, alongside a cost-effectiveness analysis and awareness-raising campaigns, will promote the adoption of CVDLINK outputs in the mid-term.

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Executive Summary

This report provides an overview of the CVDLINK project website, which comprehensively presents the project's objectives and expected outcomes, alongside the partners implementing the action.

The website was developed by Trilateral Research, but all project partners have provided feedback. The website is built as a central point for the project's dissemination and communication; links to social media, newsletter subscription, and contact information are available.

The graphic design of the website is consistent with CVDLINK's visual identity and will be updated as the project progresses.

The website for the CVDLINK project is <https://cvdlink-project.eu>

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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial intelligence
CVD	Cardiovascular diseases
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
DPO	Data protection officer
WP	Work package
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable

Glossary of terms

Term	Definition
Responsible, trustworthy AI	AI systems created to prioritise ethical principles, such as explainability, accountability, security, and non-maleficence, to enable human oversight, transparency, data protection, and privacy in the design, development, and deployment.
Federated storage	Any storage system that integrates and manages multiple, autonomous storage systems as a unified, centrally managed resource.
FAIR principles	Techniques to make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
Data subject	The individual data relates to.
Data controller	The person or entity which determines the means and purposes of processing data.

1 Introduction

CVDLINK aims to develop artificial intelligence (AI) and data-driven tools to aid in the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs). A central element of the project is integrating existing data sources, such as data held by individual hospitals or researchers, and developing approaches to ensure patient data can be shared securely. As such, the success of the project outputs relies on the development of a data sharing culture. This, in turn, relies on the promotion of trust in AI and data-driven medical tools and confidence that sensitive data can be shared safely. With these goals in mind, having a robust public presence to communicate these ideas is crucial to the project's success. The website is the centre point of this public presence, where articles, newsletters, updates, and outputs will be made available to our diverse target groups.

This deliverable summarises each section of the website. Because the project is in its early stages, some content is not yet available; for example, there is only one press release in the news section, which will later include blogs, and the page where all publications will be stored is not yet published.

2 Project website

2.1 Website structure

The project website (<http://cvdlink-project.eu/>) was launched in M06 (June 2024). At this stage, the website is designed to share key information about the project, including objectives, planned outputs, partners, and work packages. Throughout the project, the website will be updated with publications, blogs, information about events, project results, and other pertinent information. For a full overview of the website's role in dissemination and communication, refer to D8.1, the CVDLINK raising awareness and dissemination plan.

At publication, the website includes the following pages:

- Home
- About
- Project outcomes
- News
- Consortium
- Contact us

Every page includes a header with the project logo and a footer with the project's email and social media pages, the privacy and cookie policies, the coordinator's contact information, and the funding statement. A newsletter sign-up form will be added to the footer by M7.

2.1.1 Home page

The Home page is the landing page of the website. It opens with a large image and the project's tagline, "Unlocking data-driven solutions for cardiovascular care," followed by a "learn more" button which takes viewers to the About page, where they can learn about the project in more detail. The home page also includes the partners' logos and a brief description of the project's objectives.

Figure 1. CVDLINK website Home page

2.1.2 About

The About page contains two sections. The first provides a brief but detailed overview of the project, outlining the problem CVDLINK seeks to address, the project’s novel approach, and our expected outcomes. The second section defines key terminology that the general public may not be familiar with: Responsible, Trustworthy AI, Federated Storage, and the FAIR Principles. These are displayed in an interactive format. Viewers can click on each term to activate a drop-down box, which will display the full definition.

About

Pioneering data-driven solutions to pressing global health challenges

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of death worldwide, responsible for 17.9 million fatalities per year, according to the WHO. In Europe, this number is growing, incurring staggering costs to human life, healthcare systems, and society more broadly.

Figure 2. About page

Next, we’ll develop AI models which will analyse this unified dataset and produce tools to aid in the prevention, diagnosis, and risk stratification of CVDs. These will be available via CVDLINK’s Platform as a Service (PaaS), which will offer custom visualisations to healthcare practitioners and researchers in the cardiovascular domain. Finally, we’ll perform studies in five countries to validate our outputs and ensure they meet the needs of our end users.

CVDLINK pairs routine health data with cutting-edge technology to provide effective, evidence-driven interventions with the potential to transform public health. Along the way, the project’s interdisciplinary team, which includes ethicists, clinicians, tech developers, and communication experts, aims to build trust in AI and data-powered medical tools.

Responsible, Trustworthy AI	–
CVDLINK outputs will be embedded with core principles of Responsible, Trustworthy AI, including transparency, explainability, and bias mitigation. Read more about these principles here.	
Federated Storage	+
FAIR principles	+

Figure 3. Interactive boxes defining key terminology on the About page

2.1.3 Project Outcomes

The Project Outcomes section is intended to give visitors insight into how the work is split up throughout the project. The page opens with a definition of work packages (WPs), as people who have not participated in EU-funded projects may be unfamiliar with the term, and then lists each WP in the project. Like the key terms in the About page, the WPs are

listed in interactive boxes. When the user clicks each WP, a drop-down box is activated which includes more information, including the WP leader and objectives.

Figure 4. Project Outcomes page

2.1.4 News

The News section will be consistently updated (roughly once per month) with blogs outlining project objectives, theoretical underpinnings, activities, and achievements. Press releases will also be published in the news section. At the time the website was launched, one item (the first press release) was in this section. See D8.1 for a full schedule of blogs to be published here.

PRESS RELEASE: AI TO REVOLUTIONIZE CARDIOVASCULAR CARE

Figure 5. News page, featuring the first press release

2.1.5 Consortium

The consortium page lists each partner’s logo and includes hyperlinks to their institutional websites.

Figure 6. Consortium page, featuring all partners' logos and hyperlinks to their home pages

2.1.6 Contact Us

The Contact Us page is a webform where visitors can enter their names, email addresses, and a message. The page also lists the project’s email, so visitors can get in touch with the project directly.

Figure 7. Contact Us page

3 Content creation and approval

Content creation for the website will follow two streams: changes initiated by TRI as the WP8 lead and manager of the website, and changes initiated by all partners.

TRI is responsible for managing the website, and as such will create pages and amend the text as needed to reflect major outputs throughout the project (see D8.1 for more detail). All changes will be directed to the coordination team for approval before implementation. Any changes reflecting scientific findings will also be sent to the partners from the relevant WPs to review for accuracy.

Partners will be responsible for contributing blogs, which will be posted monthly. TRI has created a preliminary blog schedule, outlined in D8.1, organised around public deliverables and other project milestones. TRI will be responsible for soliciting blogs from partners and providing guidelines for blog writing. Partners will send their drafted blogs to TRI, who will edit them and then pass them on to the coordination team for final approval before publishing them on the website.

4 Newsletter subscription

The newsletter sign-up link will be displayed in the footer of every page of the website. Visitors to the page will also be directed to the sign-up link in blogs and articles on the website. For a full overview of our strategy to attract newsletter subscribers, see D8.1.

5 Funding acknowledgement

The funding acknowledgement is displayed in the footer of every page of the website and will be included in all blogs and news items published on the website

Figure 8. Footer, with funding acknowledgement and contact information

Article 17.3 of the GA (CVDLINK Consortium, 2023) stipulates that all dissemination and communication material must also include the following disclaimer:

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

As per Article 17.2 of the GA (CVDLINK Consortium, 2023), all materials must include a variation of the official EU funding logo, pictured below. These can be downloaded from the EC's download centre for visual elements https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en (European Commission, (n.d.)).

Figure 9. One of the accepted versions of the funding logo

See D8.1 for a full overview of partners' responsibilities to display the funding flag and statement on communication and dissemination materials.

6 Privacy policy

The privacy policy is displayed on the footer of the website, which is visible on every page.

The policy, which is available in Annex 9.1, outlines the following:

- How we will process the personal data of users visiting the website
- How we will manage the personal data included in the content of our website, such as information about the researchers involved in the project
- The legal bases for processing the data, as defined under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): consent, legal obligations, legitimate interests
- Data subjects' rights under the GDPR, including rights to access, to rectification, to object, and to erasure.

6.1 Cookie policy

Like the privacy policy, the cookie policy is displayed in the footer of every page on the website. The policy, which is available in Annex 9.2, outlines the following:

- How the CVDLINK website uses cookies
- Defines different types of cookies and their potential impacts on data processing and user privacy
- Describes how the different types of cookies impact the functioning of the CVDLINK website
- How the website's use of cookies interacts with user privacy and the privacy policy

7 Conclusions

This deliverable gives a brief overview of the project website, summarising the pages and content available upon the website's launch, as well as information about the newsletter sign-up, funding acknowledgement, privacy and cookie policies, and the content creation process.

The project website can be accessed at any time and provides stakeholders with up-to-date information and updates on the project progress.

A more detailed explanation of the website's role in CVDLINK's dissemination and communication strategy is included in D8.1, the CVDLINK raising awareness & dissemination plan.

8 References

CVDLINK Consortium, 2023. *Grant Agreement*, s.l.: s.n.

European Commission, (n.d.). *Download Centre for Visual Elements*. [Online] Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

9 Annexes

9.1 Privacy Policy

Introduction

Thank you for visiting the CVDLINK website. This Privacy Policy addresses processing of personal data for the operation of the website. This covers personal data that visitors provide through the website and the personal data included as part of our website content.

We are committed to processing personal data responsibly, securely, and proportionally throughout our activities in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679.

Who we are

CVDLINK is a European Union (EU)-funded Horizon Europe project that aims to securely integrate existing medical datasets to enable the development of data-driven AI tools which can help prevent, mitigate, and treat cardiovascular diseases (CVDs). As such, the work will tackle challenges associated with health data sharing, such as privacy and logistical concerns, and employ techniques to address these challenges, including federated storage. The project will use co-creative approaches to design an AI- and data-powered tool which will offer visualisations to health care providers treating CVD patients, engaging in co-creation workshops throughout the design process to include expert feedback in the development of the tools, and validating the final outputs through a series of studies with end users. Throughout the project, in-house ethical and data management experts will be involved to ensure data sharing is safe and preserves privacy.

The consortium is composed of 19 partners, including clinicians, tech developers, and ethicists. The consortium brings together essential and interdisciplinary skills and will collaborate to deliver medical technologies which are effective in practice and adhere to the most stringent legal, ethical, and privacy-preserving standards.

For the purposes of this website, the data controller is Trilateral Research IE Ltd, registered in Ireland under company number 616396, with a registered office at Marine Point, 2nd Floor, Belview Port, Waterford, X91 W0XW, Ireland. You can contact the data controller via email at DPO [at] trilateralresearch.com.

Personal data processed through the website

If you contact us through the website, we will collect your contact details and the message you provided us with. However, we will not collect metadata that you do not explicitly provide us with, such as IP/MAC addresses.

The content we upload or otherwise make available through the website may contain personal data, such as the names of our researchers and their places of work.

Legal bases of processing

We use the following legal bases for processing personal data received through the website:

Consent (Art. 6(1)(a) of the GDPR): When users consent directly to the processing of their personal data, such as by subscribing to the project newsletter. If they provide us with sensitive personal data falling under Art. 9 of the GDPR (such as dietary requirements for an event), we will process it under 9(2)(a) of the GDPR.

Legitimate Interests (Art. 6(1)(f) of the GDPR): We process personal data when it is necessary for us to achieve the following legitimate interests:

Enhancing our research delivery by providing information about CVDLINK to the individuals we consider likely to be interested in our project. This may include:

Sending invitations and providing access to guests attending our events and webinars;

Monitoring the activity on this project website.

Should the recipient of the information indicate that they would not like to receive further communications from the project, we will cease processing their personal data

We process the personal data we communicate through the website according to the following lawful bases:

- *Consent* (Art. 6(1)(a) of the GDPR) - when we have received consent to publish personal data – e.g., a blog post from one of our researchers.
- *Legal obligations* (Art. 6(1)(c) of the GDPR) - we may process personal data in order to meet a legal obligation, e.g., promoting project results to multiple audiences, including the media and the public.
- *Legitimate interests* (Art. 6(1)(f) of the GDPR) - we process personal data when it is necessary for us to achieve the following legitimate interests (if they are not overridden by the data subject's interests):
 - Enhancing our research delivery by providing information about CVDLINK activities on the website;
 - Undertaking dissemination activities.

How we secure your personal data

We have technical and organisational security policies and procedures in place to protect personal data (including sensitive personal data) from loss, misuse, alteration, or destruction. When possible, we ensure that access to personal data is password-protected and restricted to a limited number of individuals with a justified purpose to access it. Those individuals with access to the data are required to maintain confidentiality about the data. To mitigate risk, we install and regularly update all security and anti-virus software on our systems. Nevertheless, users should be aware that the security of data transmitted over the Internet cannot be completely guaranteed, and some risk remains.

How long do we retain personal data?

We retain personal data only as long as is necessary for the purposes described above. We are obligated to retain data concerning EU Horizon Europe research projects for up to five years after the EC's last payment to the consortium (further retention may be requested by EU auditors).

As the records and documentation containing personal data have been collected within the delivery of a European Commission (EC) project, we expect that the EC will process it in compliance with Regulation No 2018/1725, on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data by Union institutions, bodies, offices, and agencies. After the retention period expires, and unless further grounds for retention arise, we will dispose of personal data securely.

Do we share personal data with third parties?

The CVDLINK consortium will not share personal information with anyone except the EC, if it requests such information. All partners will treat information received from other partners as confidential and will not disclose it to anyone else, unless it is obvious that the information is already publicly available or if there is a legal obligation to do so. The partners will impose the same obligations on their employers and suppliers.

We may occasionally share personal data with trusted third parties to help us deliver our services efficiently. We will ensure that recipients are contractually bound to safeguard the data we entrust to them before sharing information. We may engage with the following categories of recipients:

- Parties that support us as we provide our services (e.g., cloud-based software services such as Dropbox, Microsoft SharePoint, Google Analytics);
- Our professional advisors, including lawyers, auditors, and insurers;
- Payment service providers;
- Email management services;
- Law enforcement and other government and regulatory agencies or other third parties as required by, and in accordance with, applicable law or regulation;
- The European Commission when we are required to do so in relation to our work on EC Horizon Europe projects.

Do we transfer your personal data outside the EU?

By default, we store personal data on servers located in the EU. However, we may also transfer personal data to reputable third-party service providers, notably SharePoint, who may be located outside of the EU.

Your rights under data protection legislation

As a data subject, you can exercise the rights outlined in this section of the privacy policy. We may need to request specific information from you to help us confirm your identity and ensure your right to access the information or to exercise any of your other rights. This helps us ensure that personal data is not disclosed to any person who has no right to receive it. No fee is required to make an initial request unless your request is clearly

unfounded or excessive. Depending on the circumstances, we may be unable to comply with your request based on other lawful grounds.

- *Right to access* (Art. 15 of the GDPR)

The data subject has the right to obtain confirmation as to whether processing of personal data concerning them takes place in the CVDLINK project. If this is the case, the data subject can request access to their data. Granting the right to access only occurs where the identification of the data subject is possible.

- *Right to rectification* (Art. 16 of the GDPR)

The data subject has the right to obtain the rectification of inaccurate personal data concerning them. The exercise of this right is only possible where the data subject can be identified and the inaccuracy of data is verified.

- *Restriction of processing* (Art. 18 of the GDPR)

The data subject has the right to obtain the restriction of processing where:

- The accuracy of the personal data is contested;
- The processing is unlawful, the data subject opposes the erasure of personal data and requests the restriction of processing instead;
- The controller no longer needs the personal data, but they are required by the data subject for the establishment, exercise, or defence of legal claims;
- The data subject has objected to processing pursuant to Art. 21(1) of the GDPR pending the verification of whether the legitimate grounds of the controller override those of the data subject.
- The exertion of this right may require provision of further information to allow identification of the data subject.
- *Right to object* (Art. 21 of the GDPR)

A legal basis for the processing of personal data in the CVDLINK project is Art. 6(1)(f) of the GDPR. The data subject has the right to object on grounds relating to their situation at any time to the processing of personal data concerning them, unless the CVDLINK consortium demonstrates compelling legitimate grounds for the processing that overrides the interests, rights, and freedoms of the data subject or for the establishment, exercise, or defence of legal claims.

The exertion of this right may require provision of further information to allow identification of the data subject.

- *Right to erasure ('Right to be forgotten')* (Art. 17 of the GDPR)

The data subject has the right to obtain erasure of personal data concerning them, if:

- The data subject objects to the processing pursuant to Art. 21(1) of the GDPR and there are no overriding legitimate grounds;
- The personal data have been unlawfully processed;
- The personal data have to be erased for compliance with a legal obligation in Union or Member State law to which the controller is subject
- *Right to data portability* (Art. 20 of the GDPR)

In some circumstances, where you have provided personal data to us, you can ask us to transmit that personal data (in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format) directly to another company.

- *Right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority* (Art. 77 of the GDPR)

The data subject has the right to lodge a complaint with a data protection supervisory authority in the Member State of their habitual residence, place of work, or place of the alleged infringement if the data subject considers that the processing of personal data relating to them infringes the GDPR.

Disclaimer and limitations of liability

We aim to keep the information that appears on the CVDLINK website as complete and updated as possible. If errors are brought to our attention, we will take all reasonable steps to ensure corrections are made within a reasonable timeframe. Please be aware that the information published on the website is for informational purposes only. None of the information published on our website is legal or professional advice, and we cannot accept responsibility for how it may be used. Further, we are not responsible or liable for any errors or omissions in any of the information provided on the website. We cannot be held liable for any direct or indirect damage that may result from use of this site. Links to other websites are provided in good faith and for information only. A link to another website does not mean that we endorse or accept any responsibility for the content or use of such a website.

While we take all possible steps to minimise disruption caused by technical errors, we cannot guarantee that our website will not be interrupted or otherwise affected by such problems. Please note that access may be suspended temporarily and without notice in the case of system failure, website maintenance, or for reasons beyond our control.

The use of our website is governed by the law of Ireland. Any dispute arising from the use of this website shall be subject to the non-exclusive jurisdiction of the Irish courts.

Do we link to other websites?

Our websites may contain links to other sites, including those of the consortium partners, which are not governed by this privacy policy. Please review the destination websites' privacy policies before submitting personal data on those sites. Whilst we try to link only to sites that share our standards and respect for privacy, we are not responsible for the content, security, or privacy practices employed by other sites.

Do we change this privacy policy?

We regularly review this privacy policy and will post any updates to it on this webpage. The privacy policy was last updated on 1 June 2024.

9.2 Cookie Policy

What is a Cookie?

A cookie is a simple text file downloaded to your computer or mobile device when you visit a website, so the website recognises your device the next time you visit. Cookies are used to improve navigation, making visitors' experiences faster, easier, and more personalised. In this policy, the term 'cookies' refers to all files that collect information in this way.

Cookies serve many functions for the operators of websites. For example, they can allow us to remember visitors' language preferences or login information, analyse how well the website is performing, and recommend content we believe is most relevant to individual visitors.

Cookies on our website

We use cookies to improve visitors' experience of the CVDLINK website. These cookies automatically track and collect technical information from visitors' browsers. This information may include Internet Protocol (IP) addresses, browser type, browser language, Internet service providers (ISP), referring/exit pages, URLs, operating systems, date/time stamps, and other similar information. However, this information does not identify individual users, and will be used exclusively to analyse trends, manage the website, and track user movements to different pages of the website to improve the services provided.

Because cookies are not strictly necessary for the website to function, users are given the option to opt out of cookie usage. We do not use cookies to track visitors once they have left the website, and the data from cookies will not be passed on to or used by any commercial enterprise that is not operating under our instruction.

How do we use cookies?

A visit to our website may generate 'first-party' cookies and 'third-party' cookies. First-party cookies are set by us and relate to the domain of our website. A third-party cookie is associated with a domain name different from that of the page the user is visiting. They are only generated with users' agreement. We use third-party cookies to provide enhanced site functionality such as embedded video content.

We use the following types of cookies:

- **Strictly necessary cookies:** These are the most important cookies, as they are essential for the operation of the site, allowing users to navigate pages and access basic features. If users opt to disable these cookies, they will not be able to access the CVDLINK website.
- **Functionality cookies:** these enable us to remember visitors and personalise their experiences on the website. They record information about choices users have made on our website in the past, such as language.
- **Performance/analytics cookies:** These are used to analyse how the website is accessed, used, and performs to provide visitors with a better user experience and

to maintain, operate, and continually improve the website. For example, these cookies allow us to better understand the profile of our website's visitors so we can improve the presentation of our content or collect general (i.e., not personal) information about website visitors, such as what browsers or devices they are using, how many are first-time visitors, etc.

Within these three categories, cookies are classified as either session or persistent cookies. 'Session' cookies are temporary and are deleted from users' devices once they close the browser window. 'Persistent' cookies remain on users' devices for a longer period and are used by the website to recognise users when they return.

Retention period of the Cookies we use

Session cookies are not retained after the browser window is closed. Functionality and performance/analytics cookies are stored by Google to 'remember' the users' interactions with the website for a period not exceeding two years.

How to control Cookies

Users have the right to choose whether to accept cookies through the website's pop-up window. Users should note that rejecting cookies may prevent them from using the full functionality of the website.

Most browsers allow users to change their cookie settings, usually in the "options" or "preferences" menu.

Change of this policy

We may change this policy to reflect changes in the law or our practices and services. We suggest users visit this policy periodically for updates.

Contact us

If you have any concerns about how your data is processed, you can contact us by email or post:

Data Protection Officer, Trilateral Research Ltd, Marine Point, 2nd Floor, Belview Port, Waterford, X91 W0XW, Ireland, or at DPO [at] trilateralresearch.com. We will respond to your queries within 30 days.

CVDLINK Project Consortium

 TUDa TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DARMSTADT						
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 SYNYO SYNYO						